

UDC 378.147: 640.41(477)

DOI: 10.15587/2519-4984.2020.217512

TRAINING OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN THE HOTEL AND RESTAURANT INDUSTRY IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF DISTANCE LEARNING

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In the present article a structural-system analysis of studying the experience of preparation of future specialists in the hotel and restaurant industry in the conditions of distance learning is carried out. Features of training of future specialists in the hotel and restaurant industry in domestic institutions of higher education are characterized. It is established that the purpose of their training is to provide the hotel industry with highly qualified staff, competitive, requested in domestic and foreign labor markets, on the basis of real public demand for services, at developing the ability to conduct quality service and customer service industry. It is determined, that professional training of future specialists in the hotel and restaurant industry is a process carried, out in higher education institutions of various forms of ownership and aimed at obtaining qualifications by students in accordance with educational and professional programs of "bachelor" and "master" levels, which will ensure competitiveness and professional mobility in the hospitality industry. We analysed normative documents of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine on the requirements for the organization of the educational process in terms of distance learning, which we identify with the individualized process, associated with gaining knowledge, skills, abilities and methods of educational and cognitive human activity through indirect interaction of participants of the educational process in a special environment, created by modern psychological and pedagogical, information and communication technologies. Principles, forms, types of educational classes, methods and technologies of teaching and learning during the organization of the educational process in the conditions of distance learning are determined. Recommendations for creation of requirements for training of future specialists in the hotel and restaurant industry in terms of distance learning were created. It is necessary to provide an educational institution with appropriate technical equipment, staff to create, maintain site and network security, enable free access to workplaces, digital competence of teachers, systematic updating of educational and methodological materials, formation and development of information culture of all participants

Keywords: hotel and restaurant economy, future specialists, distance learning, methods of teaching and learning professional disciplines

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1. Introduction

The essence of quality training of a professional, strategic directions of personality formation in the process of vocational education are formulated in regulations, in particular the National Doctrine of Education of Ukraine in the XXI century, laid down in legislative documents of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine: Laws of Ukraine "On Education", "On professional higher education", "On vocational (professional-technical) education", Concepts of implementation of state policy in the field of vocational (professional-technical) education "Modern vocational (professional-technical) education" for the period up to 2027, etc.

2. Literary review

Modern research by scientists confirms the need for such a quality of education that will allow graduates of educational institutions to enter real life freely and take an active part in the restructuring of the Ukrainian economy and society. Thus, theoretical and methodological principles of professional training of future specialists in tourism are disclosed in [1]. Formation of profes-

sional culture of future specialists in the field of restaurant business in higher education is shown in [2]. Main requirements to the methodology of teaching innovative restaurant technologies to future restaurant professionals were identified in [3]. Importance of professional training of future specialists in hotel and resort business in terms of higher education was proved in [4]. Theory and practice of training specialists in the field of tourism in the countries, members of the World Tourism Organization is disclosed in [5].

Necessity of formation of readiness of future specialists in the field of tourism for excursion activities in professional training is proved in [6]. Problems of professional training of future specialists of hotel and restaurant business are analyzed in [7]. The need for the formation of entrepreneurial competence of future specialists of the restaurant industry in vocational schools is indicated in [9].

Despite such a specific attention to the problem of training future specialists in the hotel and restaurant industry in higher education institutions, the problem of using distance learning opportunities in this process needs analysis.

3. The purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is structural and systematic research of the experience of training future specialists in the hotel and restaurant industry in terms of distance learning in higher educational institutions.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

- to characterize the peculiarities of training future specialists of the hotel and restaurant industry in higher educational institutions;
- to analyze the regulations of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine (MES of Ukraine) on the requirements for the organization of the educational process in terms of distance learning;
- to study practice of organizing the educational process in terms of distance learning, to identify the essential characteristics and new opportunities;
- provide recommendations for the creation of the necessary requirements for the training of future specialists in the hotel and restaurant industry in terms of distance learning.

4. Theoretical and methodological aspects of substantiation of learning the experience of formation of preparation of future professionals in the hotel and restaurant industry in the Ukrainian establishments of higher education in the conditions of distance learning.

The service sector is a branch of Ukrainian economy that has been developing dynamically over the past decades and includes trade, transport, financing, insurance, etc. Educational and recreational sports institutions, travel agencies, hotels and restaurants, beauty salons and special medical institutions, radio and television stations, consulting firms, museums, theaters, cinemas, shops and supermarkets belong to the service sector.

Therefore, for its proper functioning, the problem of modernization of higher professional education becomes urgent in order to create a model of the educational process, in which the best Ukrainian and foreign traditions would be optimally combined. The integration of humanistic traditions of Ukrainian pedagogy and world experience of educating a specialist, capable of active independent actions, will allow to create a dynamic, mobile, competitive model of the vocational training system.

The purpose of training future specialists in the hotel and restaurant industry in higher educational establishments is to provide the hospitality industry with highly qualified staff, competitive, in demand in Ukrainian and foreign labor markets, based on the real public demand for services, in developing the ability to provide quality service and customer service.

The specifics of the above specialists' professional activity is outlined by the growing level of competition in the hotel and restaurant industry, increased consumer demands for quality service, growing needs of employers for competent professionals, able to provide services at world standards, adapt to the changing socio-economic environment, solve professional tasks quickly and creatively.

Quite often there are serious discrepancies between conservative trends in the vocational education system and current needs of the hotel and restaurant industry for qualified professionals, which drives the need

of organization and implementation of "additional" training of graduates directly in their workplace. In the conditions of innovative development of hotel and restaurant enterprises, the need of systematic modernization of professional and practical training of future hotel and restaurant service specialists is actualized, in particular on updating the content of training, curricula of professional and practical training, revising the ratio of theoretical and practical knowledge, skills, competencies and in accordance with employers' needs.

We understand the *professional training of future specialists in the hotel and restaurant industry* as a process, carried out in higher educational institutions of various forms of ownership and aimed at obtaining qualifications in accordance with educational and professional programs of "Bachelor" and "Master" levels, that will ensure their competitiveness and professional mobility in the hospitality industry.

The readiness of a future specialist in the hotel and restaurant industry for the professional activity is analyzed as a result of training in higher educational institutions of various forms of ownership, aimed at mastering professionally oriented knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies that establish his/her compliance with requirements of hotel and restaurant enterprises by customers of educational services.

Future specialist in hotel and restaurant business is defined as a person, who, in accordance with the requirements of the Standard of Higher Education of Ukraine for the first (Bachelor) level of higher education in the field of knowledge 24 "Service", specialty 241 "Hotel and restaurant business" and educational and professional programs "Hotel and Restaurant Business" for specialist training of the second (Master's) level of higher education in the above specialty obtains higher education in accordance with the educational levels "Bachelor" and "Master" in order to carry out professional activities in hotels and restaurants.

Analyzing the changes, related to the current realities of the educational process in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and unprecedented planetary security measures through the introduction of global quarantine, it is necessary to specify the priority of the following manifestations of vocational education: modernization of information, scientific-methodological, inventory and logistical support through the use of information and communication technologies, in particular relevant in the context of today's distance learning, intellectualization and implementation of scientific and technical achievements, formation of the market of educational services and future professional mobility.

5. Results of the study

According to current regulations, *distance learning* is identified with the individualized process, associated with the acquisition of knowledge, skills, abilities and methods of educational and cognitive activities of human beings through indirect interaction of distant participants in the educational process in a special environment, created by modern psychological-pedagogical, information and communication technologies [7].

The use of the following principles in distance learning is generally accepted:

– priority of psychological-pedagogical, social and sanitary-hygienic approaches to all aspects of distance learning (information, telecommunication and other technologies should be used using didactic models of learning, taking into account psychology of a social personality and guarantee of health);

– modular approach to selection and construction of the content of distance learning, program-methodological support and organization of the educational process (application is based on compliance with the concepts of learning concepts, theory of modular learning);

– maximum possible integration of the content of distance learning (objective need to form in the minds of students holistic ideas about the world, the systemic nature of knowledge);

– formation of the information environment (web environment) in accordance with the goals, objectives and models of distance learning (freedom of search and choice of information for students, presence of specialized websites in the educational system);

– preparedness of an individual for distance learning (principle of entry level, motivation to learn, availability of basic volumes and level of knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies in computer and office equipment, means of communication knowledge);

– active feedback (meaningful, regular, operational and high-quality (technological) communication between a teacher and a student and between the participants of the training course through personal meetings, use of communication channels (post and e-mail, telephone, fax, etc.), meetings in the Internet, etc.

The educational process takes place using the following forms:

– independent work, training, practical training, control measures;

– types of educational classes: lectures, laboratory classes, practical classes, seminars, individual

classes, consultations, colloquium, training, master class, etc.

It is mandatory to provide students with the necessary educational materials through the transmission of video, audio, text and graphic information in the synchronous or asynchronous mode, online and offline communication between the persons of distance learning.

Teaching and learning methods during distance learning include demonstration, creative and problem-solving methods, educational discussion and / or debate, brainstorming, case study / situation analysis, etc. The educational process is carried out using the technology of teaching and learning: problem lectures (problem solving), visualization lectures (video demonstrations, etc.), binary lectures (two lecturers - a teacher and a practitioner), lectures with pre-planned mistakes, lectures - press conferences, searching laboratory work, research work, heuristic conversation, role and business games, educational games, trainings in an active mode, analysis of concrete situations, Case study, solving inventive tasks, analysis of business mail.

Own practical experience of conducting educational and cognitive activities in distance learning, as well as teachers of hotel and restaurant and tourism business of Kherson State University allows the implementation of analytical and synthetic research on the organization of the above mentioned educational process, in particular during the study of professional disciplines. Education of students is carried out through the use of online communications and digital interactions: sites, blogs, forums, chats, dialogues or correspondence, conferences using traditional means of the Internet communication: Skype, Facebook, Messenger, Telegram, Viber, YouTube, Google -class, various platforms, including Zoom.us, Cisco Webex Meetings, Google Classroom, Moodle, Microsoft Teams, Discord, etc. The method of implementation of the educational process by teachers of the department is given in Table 1.

Table 1

Methods of teaching and learning professional disciplines

Disciplines	
Technology of restaurant industry products	
1	2
<i>Types of classes</i>	Lecture-presentation, lecture-visualization, practical session, laboratory practicals, individual lesson, individual consultations, master class.
<i>Methods, technologies of teaching and learning</i>	Electronic texts and publications, multimedia, television, videos, individual practical tasks (development of technological maps of dishes and cooking at home, observing technologies), individual videos of presentations, plots, videos, videocasts, educational channels.
<i>Teaching aids</i>	Computers, computer systems and networks, World Wide Web, YouTube, web forum, video chat.
Basics of culinary art	
<i>Types of classes</i>	Lecture-exchange of experience, lecture-visualization, practical session, laboratory practicals, individual consultations, master class.
<i>Methods, technologies of teaching and learning</i>	Creative, problem-searching, demonstration, situation analysis. Computer training programs, computer training, online video chat, training videos, individual videos of presentations of protection of own product.

Continuation of Table 1

1	2
Commodity science and food quality control	
<i>Types of classes</i>	Problem lecture, lecture-presentation, practical session, individual lesson, individual consultations, test, colloquium.
<i>Methods, technologies of teaching and learning</i>	Problem-searching, educational discussion. Analysis of specific situations, solution of research tasks, analytical note (on the topic of individual practical task), multimedia, news, speeches, video casts, educational channels, programs, commercials.
<i>Teaching aids</i>	Computers, computer systems and networks, graphics tools, online platforms for non-formal education (KSU Online, Prometheus, Universe), YuoTube, web forum.
Hygiene and sanitation in the industry	
<i>Types of classes</i>	Lecture-presentation, lecture-meeting, practical session.
<i>Methods, technologies of teaching and learning</i>	Educational discussion, situation analysis, project method (group practical / research task). Analysis of specific situations, solving research problems, online conferences with the representation of group practical / research projects.
<i>Teaching aids</i>	Multimedia, video and sound-producing, projection equipment, video cameras, projectors, screens), devices and equipment, sites of the State Food and Consumer Service
Standardization, certification and metrology	
<i>Types of classes</i>	Problem lecture, lecture-exchange of experience, practical session.
<i>Methods, technologies of teaching and learning</i>	Problem-searching, educational discussion, project method. Solving research tasks, defence of individual projects - drawing up a scheme of production of culinary products, for which technical conditions (TC) are developed; analytical note (on the topic of individual practical task).
<i>Teaching aids</i>	Computers, computer systems and networks, sites of the International Organization for Standardization, SE "Khersonstandartmetrologiya".
International quality standards of hotel and restaurant business	
<i>Types of classes</i>	Problem lecture, practical session, online training, lecture-exchange of experience (guest lecturer), binary lecture
<i>Methods, technologies of teaching and learning</i>	Problem-searching, educational discussion, situation analysis. Electronic texts and publications, computer training programs, online conferences, online video chat, news, speeches.
<i>Teaching aids</i>	Computers, computer systems and networks, telecommunication networks, graphic tools.
Organization of restaurant business	
<i>Types of classes</i>	Lecture-presentation, lecture-discussion, practical session, individual lesson, master class.
<i>Methods, technologies of teaching and learning</i>	Educational discussion, situation analysis, demonstration. Computer training programs, virtual reality and modeling (online restaurant broadcast), stories, videos, television, video films, video castings, training channels.
<i>Teaching aids</i>	Computers, computer systems and networks; software (to support distance learning, online survey, virtual restaurant, to create computer graphics, modeling); hotel and food complexes (dining rooms, cafeterias, restaurants, hotels) ("RUBA HUB" Kherson).

Therefore, to carry out the educational process in the conditions of distance learning in order to form a personality of a future specialist during getting vocational education, an educational institution must be provided with appropriate technical equipment, adequate staffing to create, maintain the site and network security, be able to give free access to all working places, the level of digital competence of teachers, systematic updating of educational and methodical materials, able to form and develop the information culture of all participants in educational and cognitive activities.

5. Conclusions

1. Peculiarities of training future specialists of hotel and restaurant industry in higher education institutions are characterized, definitions of concepts "pro-

fessional training of future specialists of hotel and restaurant industry", "preparation of future specialists of hotel and restaurant industry for professional activity", "future specialist of hotel and restaurant industry" are formulated.

2. Normative documents of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine (MES of Ukraine) on the requirements for the organization of the educational process in terms of distance learning are analyzed, its principles, forms, types of classes, methods and technologies of teaching and learning are determined.

3. Practice of organizing the educational process in terms of distance learning is generalized, essential characteristics concerning the use of principles (priority of psychological-pedagogical, social and sanitary-hygienic approaches; modular approach to selection and

construction of distance learning content, software and methodological support and organization of the educational process, integration of the content of distance learning, formation of the information environment, readiness of an individual for distance learning, active feedback) and new opportunities to combine forms of learning are given.

4. Recommendations are given to create the necessary requirements for the training of future specialists in the hotel and restaurant industry in higher educational establishments in distance learning, which provided for the choice of types of classes, methods, technologies of teaching and learning, teaching aids in certain disciplines.

References

1. Bezkorovaina, L. V. (2018). Teoretychni i metodychni zasady profesiinoi pidhotovky maibutnikh fakhivtsiv z turyzmoznavstva u vyshchyykh navchalnykh zakladakh. Zaporizhzhia, 698.
2. Bezruchenkov, Yu. V. (2014). The Formation of professional culture of future experts in restaurant business in higher educational institution. Luhansk, 20.
3. Vasylenko, O. V. (2016). Methods of teaching innovative restaurant technologies to future restaurant business professionals at higher education establishments. Kyiv, 242.
4. Vindiuk, A. V. (2011). Profesiina pidhotovka maibutnikh fakhivtsiv z hotelno-kurortnoi spravy v umovakh stupenevoi osvity: teoriia ta metodyka. Zaporizhzhia: KPU, 340.
5. Knodel, L. V. (2007). Teoriia i praktyka pidhotovky fakhivtsiv sfery turyzmu v krainakh-chlenakh Vsesvitnoi turystskoi orhanizatsii. Ternopil, 40.
6. Litovka-Demenina, S. H. (2018). Formuvannia hotovnosti maibutnikh fakhivtsiv sfery turyzmu do ekskursiinoi diialnosti v protsesi profesiinoi pidhotovky. Kyiv, 278.
7. Pro zatverdzhennia Polozhennia pro dystantsiine navchannia (2013). Miniust Ukrainy No. 466. 25.04.2013. Available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0703-13#Text>
8. Ponochovna-Rysak, T. M. (2019). The problems of professional training of future specialists of hotel and catering. Pedagogika formuvannia tvorchoi osobystosti u vyshchii i zahalnoosvitnii shkolakh, 1 (62), 66–69.
9. Tkachenko, M. V. (2018). Formuvannia pidpriemnytskoi kompetentnosti maibutnikh fakhivtsiv restorannoho hospodarstva u profesiino-tekhnichnykh navchalnykh zakladakh. Kyiv, 20.
10. Fedorchenko, V. K.; Nychkalo, N. H., Fedorchenko, V. K. (Eds.) (2004). Teoretychni ta metodychni zasady pidhotovky fakhivtsiv dlia sfery turyzmu. Kyiv: Slovo, 472.
11. Yakymchuk, D., Dzyundzha, O., Burak, V., Shvets, I., Shvets, Y., Myrhorodska, N. et. al. (2018). Economic efficiency of textile materials cutting designer costumes of hospitality facilities. *Vlakna a textil*, 25 (4), 45–65.

Received date 06.10.2020

Accepted date 17.11.2020

Published date 25.12.2020

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